

In-Plane Permeability of VARI Consumables: A Comparison of Experimental and Virtual Estimation Methods

E. Fauster, T. Schmidt, S. Cassola, C. Obertscheider, M. Bender, C. Lira, M. Duhovic, D. May

24th International Conference on Composites Materials (ICCM24), August 4, 2025, Baltimore

Move mountains

Contents

- Motivation
- Materials
- Experimental Work
- Results
- Conclusions
- Future Work

Motivation

- Vacuum-Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI):
 - Highly inhomogeneous setup of:
 - fibrous reinforcement in combination with
 - single layers of peely ply and flow distribution media
 - Significant differences in permeability
- Aim
 - Full coverage of flow related mechanisms in flow simulation software
 - Methodological comparison of methods for estimating in-plane permeability

VARI Consumable Materials

- Flow distribution media (FM)
 - Airtech Knitflow 105 HT
 - Polyester knitted fabric
 - Areal weight: 105 g/m²

- Peel ply (PP)
 - Airtech 60BR
 - Nylon woven fabric, silicone coating
 - Areal weight: 60 g/m²

Determination of Ply Thickness

- Compressibility tests @ MUL
 - Loading at 0.01 mm/min
 - Holding at constant force (equivalent to 1 bar of vacuum pressure) for 15 min
 - Unloading at 0.01 mm/min
- Ply thickness (5 rep.)
 - FM: $0.573 \pm 0.015 \text{ mm}$
 - PP: $0.096 \pm 0.001 \text{ mm}$

Experimental Work

- In-plane permeability estimation
 - Experimental approach
 - Reverse engineering approach
 - Virtual approach

Experimental Approach - Workflow

Experimental Approach

- Experiments @ MUL
 - Radial flow experiments with optical tracking of flow front advancement
 - Plant oil with dynamic viscosity of about 65 mPas at $21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 - Measurement of fluid pressure and temperature in the feed line

- Cavity height and fiber volume content
 - FM: $h_{DM} = 0.57 \text{ mm}$ $\varphi_{DM} = 13.20 \%$
 - PP: $h_{PP} = 0.09 \text{ mm}$ $\varphi_{PP} = 61.35 \%$

Experimental Approach

- Digital image processing @ MUL

Evaluation of a test on a FM sample

Evaluation of a test on a PP sample

Experimental Approach

- Data processing @ MUL
 - Elliptic paraboloid method

- In-plane permeability of FM (3 rep.)
 - $k_1 = 10.32 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 7.01 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$

- In-plane permeability of PP (3 rep.)
 - $k_1 = 91.81 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 69.95 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$

Results of a test on a FM sample

Reverse Engineering - Workflow

Reverse Engineering - Geometry

- Flow simulations @ IVW
 - Input data from radial flow experiments @MUL

Dimensions and BCs

Reverse Engineering - Data Processing

- Data processing @ MUL
 - Elliptic paraboloid method

- In-plane permeability of FM
 - $k_1 = 10.23 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 6.91 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$

- In-plane permeability of PP
 - $k_1 = 88.72 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 68.36 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$

Results from simulation run on FM

Virtual Approach

Virtual Approach

- μ CT scans @ IVW

μ CT scan of
FM sample

μ CT scan of
PP sample

Virtual Approach - Models

- Virtual material models

FM sample

PP sample

Virtual Approach – Data Processing

- Flow simulations @ IVW
 - Flow velocity fields in x and y

- In-plane permeability of FM
 - $k_1 = 11.76 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 6.84 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$

- In-plane permeability of PP
 - $k_1 = 32.00 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$
 - $k_2 = 24.00 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$

FM sample

PP sample

Results

In-plane permeability of FM

In-plane permeability of PP

Conclusions

- Experimental approach and reverse engineering approach show well comparable results
- Virtual approach shows agreement with other approaches for the model of the flow distribution media only
- In the peel ply model, insufficient level of data segmentation leads to significant deviations

Future Work

- Improving virtual models by enhancing the level of fidelity in the data segmentation
- Extension of the comparison to stacks of FM and PP
 - Incorporation of flow effects in transverse direction

ewald.fauster@unileoben.ac.at

Thanks for your attention!

